

**● Metadata and Terminology Services. A
Toolchain for comprehensive Data- and
Knowledge Management
NFDI4Ing Conference 2022**

Agenda

- **Introduction S-3** (Felix Engel)
- **S-3 Services**
 - Terminology Service (Felix Engel)
 - Application Profile (Matthias Grönewald)
 - Metadata Hub (Benedikt Heinrichs)
- **Example Application**
 - Generate profile compliant data (Matthias Grönewald, Nils Preuß)
 - Make existing profile-compliant data available (Benedikt Heinrichs)
- **Discussion**

Introduction

- **Research data** can only be **reused** if they are described in a way that is comprehensive, interpretable and comprehensible to outsiders.
- No data and knowledge management can lead to data incompatibility and loss

Introduction

Simplified Vision: Measure S-3 “Metadata and terminology services”

NFDI4ing Measure S-3: Provide **sophisticated tools** for tagging research data with metadata, to make it available for **reuse**

1. **Generating** metadata records
2. ... by means of **access** to existing schemas
3. ... using **different repositories** for publication

Introduction

S-3 will provide a toolchain of: ... services to facilitate the creation of subject and application specific standardised metadata and their integration into engineering workflows

<u>Application Profiles</u>	<u>Terminology Service</u>	<u>Metadata Hub</u>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task S-3-1 • TUDA, RWTH, KIT 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task S-3-2 • TIB 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Task S-3-3 • TUDA, RWTH, KIT
<p>Aim: Flexible modelling of user specific schemes with maximum re-usability and interoperability</p> <p>Solution: Flexible application-specific selection of suitable elements from controlled terminologies → Application Profiles</p>	<p>Aim: Build a technical infrastructure for terminology management and access</p> <p>Solution: Provision of a web based service, that enables access, curation, and subscription to domain specific terminologies</p>	<p>Aim: Data Management of metadata documents</p> <p>Challenge:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Techn. diversity • Inconsistency of the functionalities <p>Solution: Repository turntable: Uniform access through uniform API</p>

Research Data Lifecycle

● **Phases: Planning, Production, Analysis, Storage, Access, Re-Use**

● Example (*)

● 150 --> **just a number**

● 150°C *am Karolingerplatz* --> **Nr. + Context = Information**

● Which measuring instrument is used?

● Which configurations? (characteristics, tolerances, ...)

→ **How to Re-Use** your research without having knowledge about its creation?

→ Comprehensive **metadata** is required to make your research **reproducible** and therefore **reusable**

(*) https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/education/data-life-cycle/-/blob/main/NFDI4Ing_Training_DLC_2_Daten_erheben.pdf

Planning, **Production**, Analysis,
Storage, Access, **Re-Use**

Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

1. **Domain** specific (Engineering, Culture, Chemistry...) and **community** specific
2. **Evolving** continuously and dynamically over time
3. Must be accepted, developed and maintained by a **designated community** (avoid isolated solution!) Includes a.o.
 - a) promotion (make community aware of its existence)
 - b) aligned with further metadata initiatives (moving away from silos)
 - c) applicable in RDM (in RDM practise)

—● NFDI supports terminology development and use through introduction of community specific **Terminology Services**

Planning, **Production**, Analysis,
Storage, Access, **Re-Use**

Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

- In general: A Terminology Service is a web based platform that support take-up and standardisation of terminologies
- Used by **RDM tools** and **Knowledge Workers** as
 - **Entry Point** to prepare research data for effective later reuse
 - Tag/index with keywords from an terminologies (e.g. content indexation for retrieval)
 - Consolidate terminology: use the same keywords
 - Trace changes meaning
 - Search: Query reformulation, term suggestion, ...
 - **Hub**, that fosters awareness and alignment
 - Bundles terminologies of a domain
 - Provides meta data and statistics
 - Foster alignments

EMBL-EBI

Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

- **NFDI4Ing TS:** <https://terminology.nfdi4ing.de>
- **Some statistics**
 - 31 Terminologies
 - 4,089 properties
- **Functional service offer**
 - Freetext search searching (for- and within ontologies)
 - Browsing and filtering
 - Visualisation
 - Issue tracker
 - Machine to machine communication (REST interfaces)
 - Collection management

The screenshot shows the NFDI4Ing Terminology Service website. The header includes the NFDI4Ing logo and navigation links: Home, Ontologies, FAQ, Documentation, Usage, and About. The main content area has a welcome message and a search bar with the text 'Search TS...'. Below the search bar are examples: 'electric vehicle, agent' and a link 'Looking for a particular ontology?'. There are two main sections: 'About NFDI4Ing Terminology Service' and 'Community Vision of NFDI4Ing'. The 'About' section states that the service is a repository for engineering ontologies and is developed and maintained by TIB. The 'Community Vision' section states that the service is a community-driven offer and encourages everyone interested in shaping it to propose new ontologies and features. On the right side, there is a 'Data Content' section with a bar chart icon, updated on 08 Sep 2022 09:10, and statistics: 31 ontologies, 12,798 terms, 4,122 properties, and 10,145 individuals. Below that is a 'Tweets from @NFDI4Ing' section with a tweet from @NFDI4Ing dated 19h, mentioning a talk by Jürgen Windeck at TU DA and providing a link to register for the talk.

Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

List of all ontologies in the Terminology Service

Ontology Name	Short name	Description	Loaded	Action
Basic Formal Ontology	BFO	The upper level ontology upon which OBO Foundry ontologies are built.	Thu Oct 28 16:55:15 GMT 2021	Search Terms Properties Individuals
Bioinformatics operations, data types, formats, identifiers and topics	EDAM	EDAM is a simple ontology of well established, familiar concepts that are prevalent within bioinformatics, including types of data and data identifiers, data formats, operations and topics. EDAM provides a set of terms with synonyms and definitions - organised into an intuitive hierarchy for convenient use.	Thu Oct 28 16:57:03 GMT 2021	Search Terms Properties Individuals
Building Topology Ontology	bot	The Building Topology Ontology (BOT) is a minimal ontology for describing the core topological concepts of a building.	Thu Oct 28 16:55:17 GMT 2021	Search Terms Properties Individuals
Core Ontology for Robotics and Automation (CORA)	CORA	This is the OWL implementation of CORA in IEEE 1872-2015. It only includes the taxonomy of concepts and relations, with some few axioms regarding disjointness, property characteristics and property ranges/domains. The OWL implementation is an underspecified version of the SUO-KIF implementation in IEEE 1872-2015. That is, the set of allowed models of the SUO-KIF implementation is a proper subset of the allowed models by the OWL implementation.	Thu Oct 28 16:56:10 GMT 2021	Search Terms Properties Individuals
Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV)	dpv	The Data Privacy Vocabulary (DPV) provides terms (classes and properties) to describe and represent information related to processing of personal data based on established requirements such as for the EU General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). The DPV is structured as a	Thu Oct 28 16:56:45 GMT 2021	Search Terms Properties Individuals

electric vehicle

Exact match Obsolete terms

Search results for electric vehicle

Previous Showing 1 to 10 of 219 results Next

electric vehicle **OEO:00000146**
http://openenergy-platform.org/ontology/oeo/OEO_00000146
Ontology: [Repository for the Open Energy Ontology \(OEO\)](#) **OEO**

Electric Vehicle **ElectricVehicle**
<http://schema.mobivoc.org/#ElectricVehicle>
Ontology: [MobiVoc Open Mobility Vocabulary](#) **MV**

Electric Vehicle Charging **Electric_Vehicle:Charging**
http://www.w3id.org/ecsel-dr-PWR#Electric_Vehicle_Charging
Ontology: [Digital Reference](#) **dr**

Term type

Filter by type

- class **110**
- individual **94**
- property **45**

Ontology

- Basic Formal Ontology (BFO)
- Building Topology Ontology (bot)
- Core Ontology for Robotics and Automation (CORA)

Planning, **Production**, Analysis,
Storage, Access, **Re-Use**

Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

- Example **M2M** Communication
- Creation and sharing of metadata standards as so-called **Application Profiles**
- An application profile is a set of requirements for subject and use-case specific metadata and represented in RDF and SHACL
- Within the frontend, users can search and drag vocabulary terms into their application profile as properties. The TIB Terminology Service is used to retrieve these vocabulary terms, by automatically querying its **REST Interface**

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Metadata and Terminology Services

Terminology Service

- How we **differ from plain OLS** (an extract)
 - new and tailored **frontend**
 - extended **REST** interface incl. **Swagger** documentation
 - **collection management**
 - **CI Pipeline**
 - Ingestion pipeline to **check/validate ontologies**
- TS is a complex project. Currently only one NFDI4Ing developer.
Joined forces with:
 - **NFDI4Chem**: REACT based frontend
 - **CoyPu**: WebProtege-Git integration
 - **FairDS**: Integration of ontologie analysis tools

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Metadata and Terminology Services

Application Profiles

- **General description:** An online platform for generating and sharing metadata profiles
- Profiles allow for specific but interoperable metadata
- Focusing on controlled vocabularies creates conformity with existing domain knowledge
- **Service offer:** *Unified online platform for human- and machine readable metadata* – **Metadata Profile Service**

The screenshot shows the AIM5 web interface. On the left, there's a list of 'Verfügbare Applikationsprofile' with 'machine tool axis' selected. In the center, there's a 'Vokabularterme' section with a search for 'position' and a list of terms like 'position', 'route_position', etc. On the right, there's a 'Detailsansicht' for 'machine tool axis' showing fields like 'name', 'physical unit', 'quantity kind', 'position', and 'range'. Below the screenshot, there's a code editor window showing a snippet of Turtle (data.ttl) code:

```
6 ex:TemperatureReading
7   qudt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Temperature ;
8   qudt:applicableUnit unit:DEG_C ;
9   schema:value "20.54513"^^xsd:float .
```


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Metadata and Terminology Services

Application Profiles

- **User interaction:** *Build, retrieve and share schemas*
- Search for metadata profiles and related metadata
- Re-use, adapt and refine schemas based on controlled vocabularies
- Share schemas and publish metadata (via S3-3)
- Community-based curation of domain-specific metadata profiles
- **Technologies:** SHACL profiles, flexible serialisation (JSON-LD, TTL, XML, etc.)

The screenshot shows the AIMS web interface. The left panel displays 'Verfügbare Applikationsprofile' with a search bar and a list of profiles including 'property', 'quantity', 'system', 'platform', 'feature of interest', 'observation', 'processing step', 'sensor', 'machine tool axis', 'range', 'Machine Tool', and 'humidity measurement'. The middle panel shows 'Vokabularterme' with a search bar and a list of terms including 'position', 'route_position', 'time:time_position', 'has_fabric_position', 'time:time_position', 'time:nominal_position', 'time:numeric_position', 'SIO_000211', and 'SIO_000242'. The right panel shows 'Detailsansicht' for the 'machine tool axis' profile, with a table of properties: 'name' (http://qudt.org/schemas/qudt/units/physical-unit), 'physical unit' (http://qudt.org/schemas/qudt/units/physical-unit), 'quantity kind' (qudt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Temperature), 'position' (qudt:applicableUnit unit:DEG_C), and 'range'. The bottom right panel shows a code editor with the following TTL code:

```
data.ttl
6 ex:TemperatureReading
7   qudt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Temperature ;
8   qudt:applicableUnit unit:DEG_C ;
9   schema:value "20.54513"^^xsd:float .
```


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Metadata and Terminology Services

Application Profiles

Search & Re-use

Available Application Profiles

measurement
humidity measurement
length measurement
angle measurement
temperature measurement
measurement
pressure measurement

Vocabulary Terms

has unit	
SIO_000221	●
OEO_00040010	●
hasUnit	●
org_has_unit	●
hasUnit	●
IAO_0000039	●
IAO_0000407	●
has_sub_unit	●
has_data_transmission_unit	●
hasBaseUnit	●

Detail View: temperature measurement

Show Relationships

Current Application Profile: **temperature measurement**

Inherited Application Profiles: measurement

http://qudt.org/schema/qudt/hasQuantityKind

Refine & Adapt

Domain specific requirements

Field Properties

Term IRI

Field Name

Minimum Required Entries

Maximum Possible Entries

Position On Metadata Form

Property Type

Datatype

Refine & Adapt

```

machine_tool.ttl

mt:MachineToolShape
  a sh:NodeShape ;
  dcterms:title "Machine Tool"@en ;
  dcterms:description "Milling machine" ;
  dcterms:creator "Matthias Bodenbenner" ;
  dcterms:rights "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0.html" ;
  dcterms:date "2022-06-22"^^xsd:date ;
  owl:imports aims:PlatformShape ;
  sh:node_aims:PlatformShape ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path qb:order ;
    sh:name "kinematic chain"@en ;
    sh:description "The machines kinematic chain according to ISO 841." ;
    sh:minCount 1 ;
    sh:maxCount 1 ;
    sh:datatype xsd:string ;
  ] ;
  sh:property [
    sh:path sosa:hosts ;
    sh:name "Machine Tool axes"@en ;
    sh:description "An axis of the machine." ;
    sh:qualifiedValueShape mt:MachineAxisShape ;
  ] ;
  
```


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Metadata and Terminology Services

Application Profiles

Forms

Metadaten-Formular

b6_c14n1 +

kinematic chain * ✓ +

name * ✓ +

manufacturer * ✓ +

serial number * ✓ +

Metadaten-Ansicht

```

@prefix qb: <http://purl.org/linked-data/cube#> .
@prefix rdf: <http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-ns#> .
@prefix schema: <http://schema.org/> .

_:b55 a <http://www.iot.v2i-mq.rwth-aachen.de/terms/machine-tools#MachineTool>
qb:order "1" ;
schema:name "Machine Tool 1" ;
schema:manufacturer "Manufacturer" ;
schema:serialNumber "1234567890" .
                    
```

Senden

Libraries


```

20 sh:node aims:PlatformShape ;
21 sh:property [
22   sh:path qb:order ;
23   sh:range <http://schema.org/Integer> .
24 ] ;
25 acquisition.ttl                                ding to ISO 841." ;
26
27 radian:TargetPosition
28   qdt:hasQuantityKind quantityKind:Length ;
29   qdt:applicableUnit unit:M ;
30   ssn-system:hasSystemCapability radian:TargetRange ;
31   sem:hasTimeStamp "2021-11-02T13:56:38.532Z" ;
32   qdt:standardUncertainty ("0.0008869218"^^xsd:float "0.0008869218"^^xsd:float "0.0008869218"^^xsd:float) ;
33   schema:value ("0.226959617"^^xsd:float "0.3074850568"^^xsd:float) ;
34   rdfs:label "Kalibrierung einer Werkzeugmaschine" .
35
    
```


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Metadata and Terminology Services

Application Profiles

- **Goal:** More accessible metadata management to facilitate wider application of rich metadata and foster metadata standards.
- Complex profiles are far more powerful, but harder to manage.
- *Metadata Profile Service* will offer a platform for the community to collaborate on them.
- Toolchain relation: Make terms and content vom TS applicable, allow for even richer metadata description in MH

**Complex machine-actionable
profile of a sensor**

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Metadata and Terminology Services

Metadata Hub

- Metadata repositories usually provide different interfaces
- Interoperability is wanted but cannot be achieved like this
- Goal:
 - Bring them together
- How:
 - A generic interface which combines different kinds of metadata repositories with one standard-based interface

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Metadata and Terminology Services

Metadata Hub

- Solution: The Metadata Hub
(<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/s-3/s-3-3/metadatahub>)
- Brings together
 - AIMS
 - Coscine
 - MetaStore
 - Your Solution?

Metadata and Terminology Services

Metadata Hub

- For access => Turntable API
(<https://nfdi4ing.pages.rwth-aachen.de/s-3/s-3-3/turntable-interface/>)
- Standard-based API which gives methods for metadata and schemas (application profiles)
 - Create
 - Read
 - Update
 - Delete
 - List
 - Validate

Metadata and Terminology Services

Metadata Hub

- Defined mappings
- Since services are very different
- Mappings needed to be created for the individual services
- In a first step, Coscine and Metastore were mapped
- Especially, the difference between JSON/XML Schema and SHACL Application Profiles made this a challenge

Metadata and Terminology Services

Metadata Hub

- How to use it?
(<https://git.rwth-aachen.de/nfdi4ing/s-3/s-3-3-3/metadatahubdemonstrator>)
- A demonstrating UI has been developed
- Different Metadata Repositories can be selected
- A request (like "Read") can be chosen
- With a request like "Read" metadata will be returned

MetadataHub Demonstrator

Select the targeted provider

Coscine

Input your User Token

eyJhbGciOiJIUzI1NiIsInR5cCI6IWRXVjE5LWVzZC00OWQ5LTkzZDZlZjFkMDQ4MGM2NDk0IiwiaWF0IjoiYHR0cHM6Ly9jb3NjaWw!

Select the wanted method

Read

Select the wanted type

Schema

Input the metadata path

https://purl.org/coscine/ap/radar/

Send Request

Response

```
{
  "id": "schema",
  "value": "[{"@id": "https://purl.org/coscine/ap/radar/", "@graph":
    [{"@id": "https://purl.org/coscine/ap/radar#subject", "http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#path":
      [{"@id": "http://purl.org/dc/terms/subject"}, {"http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#order":
        [{"@value": "3"}, {"@type": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#integer"}]}, {"http://www.w3.org/ns/shacl#maxCount":
```


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Storage, Access, **Re-Use**

Metadata and Terminology Services

M4I Ontology

- **General description:** provide users with classes and properties to describe a data-generating research activity and its participants, inputs, variables and outputs.
- **User interaction:**
 - **Retrieve** stable, persistent ontology versions, serialisations and versioned documentation
 - **Find** application examples and training materials (WIP)
 - **Create** application profiles and RDF-based metadata
 - Re-Use during **creation** of more specific engineering ontologies

S-3 Service interplay

Building a metadata profile for a measurement result

20.54513 °C
e.g.
Result in
deg. C

```
9  aims:QuantityValueShape
10  a sh:NodeShape ;
11
12  dcterms:subject dfgfo:4 ;
13  dcterms:title "quantity value"@en ;
14  dcterms:description ""A Quantity Value expresses the magnitude and kind of a quantity and is given by the product
15  | of a numerical value n and a unit of measure U. The number multiplying the unit is referred to
16  | as the numerical value of the quantity expressed in that unit. Refer to NIST SP 811 section 7
17  | for more on quantity values."" ;
18  dcterms:creator "Nils Preuß" ;
19  dcterms:rights "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0.html" ;
20  dcterms:created "2022-04-07"^^xsd:date ;
21
22  sh:property [
23    sh:path qdat:unit ;
24    sh:name "unit"@en ;
25    sh:description ""Relation to a a unit of measure, or unit, which is a particular quantity value that has been
26    | chosen as a scale for measuring other quantities the same kind."" ;
27    sh:minCount 1 ;
28    sh:maxCount 1 ;
29    sh:class qdat:Unit ;
30  ] ;
31
32  sh:property [
33    sh:path qdat:numericValue ;
34    sh:name "numeric value"@en ;
35    sh:description "Relation of an observable thing to its values, or reference to location where values are stored." ;
36    sh:minCount 1 ;
37    sh:maxCount 1 ;
38  ] ;
39
```

Profile info

Result must state a legit unit

Result must state or reference a numeric value

Building a metadata profile for a measurement result

20.54513 °C
e.g.
Result in
deg. C

```

9  aims:QuantityValueShape
10  a sh:Node
11
12  dcterm:su
13  dcterm:s:ti
14  dcterm:s:de
15
16
17
18  dcterm:s:cr
19  dcterm:s:r
20  dcterm:s:cr
    
```

Profile info

URL des Applikationsprofils

Titel en

Beschreibung en

Ersteller

Erstelldatum

expresses the magnitude and kind of a quantity and is given by the product and a unit of measure U. The number multiplying the unit is referred to of the quantity expressed in that unit. Refer to NIST SP 811 section 7 values." ;

C0-1.0.html" ;

Result must state a legit unit

Detailansicht 25.10.2022, 13:44:33

has unit

Feld Eigenschaften

Term IRI

Feld Name de

Minimale Erforderliche Einträge

asure, or unit, which is a particular quantity value that has been g other quantities the same kind." ;

Result must state or reference a numeric value

Applikationsprofil

nsprofile

has numerical value:
Represents the numerical value of a real
(<http://w3id.org/nfdi4ing/metadata4ing#hasNumericalValue>)

t point of a machine tool.

Vokabularterme

numerical|

- hasNumericalValue
- hasNumericalValue
- hasUnit

Detailansicht 25.10.2022, 13:44:33

has unit

ng to its values, or reference to location where values are stored." ;

Building a metadata profile for a measurement

20.54513 °C

e.g.
Result in
deg. C

e.g.
Temperature
Measurement

```
9   aims:ObservationShape
10  a sh:NodeShape ;
11  sh:targetClass sosa:Observation ;
12
13  dcterms:subject dfgfo:4 ;
14  dcterms:title "observation"@en ;
15  dcterms:description ""Act of carrying out an (Observation) Procedure to estimate or calculate a value of a property of a FeatureOfInterest
16                      Links to a Sensor to describe what made the Observation and how; links to an ObservableProperty to describe what the r
17                      is an estimate of, and to a FeatureOfInterest to detail what that property was associated with."" ;
18  dcterms:creator "Nils Preuß" ;
19  dcterms:rights "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0.html" ;
20  dcterms:created "2022-04-07"^^xsd:date ;
21
22  sh:property [
23    sh:path sosa:madeBySensor ;
24    sh:name "made by sensor"@en ;
25    sh:description "Relation between an Observation and the Sensor which made the Observations." ;
26    sh:minCount 1 ;
27    sh:maxCount 1 ;
28    sh:node aims:SensorShape ;
29  ] ;
30  owl:imports aims:SensorShape ;
31
32  sh:property [
33    sh:path sosa:hasResult ;
34    sh:name "has result"@en ;
35    sh:description "Relation linking an Observation and a Sensor, which contains a value representing the value associated with the observ
36    sh:minCount 1 ;
37    sh:node aims:QuantityValueShape ;
38  ] ;
39  owl:imports aims:QuantityValueShape .
40
```

profile info

Measurement must be linked to metadata
for sensor that made the measurement

Measurement must be linked to metadata
for the measurement result as a quantity value

Building a metadata profile for a sensor

20.54513 °C

e.g.
Result in
deg. C

e.g.
Temperature
Measurement

e.g.
Temperature
Sensor

```
10 aims:SensorShape
11   a sh:NodeShape ;
12   sh:targetClass sosa:Sensor ;
13
14   dcterms:subject dfgfo:4 ;
15   dcterms:title "sensor"@en ;
16   dcterms:description ""Device, agent (including humans), or software (simulation) involved in, or implementing, a Procedure.
17                       Sensors respond to a stimulus, e.g., a change in the environment, or input data composed from the results
18                       of prior Observations, and generate a Result. Sensors can be hosted by Platforms."" ;
19   dcterms:creator "Nils Preuß" ;
20   dcterms:rights "https://spdx.org/licenses/CC0-1.0.html" ;
21   dcterms:created "2022-10-26"^^xsd:date ;
22
23   sh:property [
24     sh:path ssn-system:hasSystemCapability ;
25     sh:name "system capability"@en ;
26     sh:description "Relation from a System to a SystemCapability describing the capabilities of the System under certain Conditions." ;
27     sh:maxCount 1 ;
28     sh:node aims:SensorCapabilityShape ;
29   ] ;
30   owl:imports aims:SensorCapabilityShape ;
31
32   sh:property [
33     sh:path sosa:observes ;
34     sh:name "observes"@en ;
35     sh:description "Relation between a Sensor and an ObservableProperty that it is capable of sensing." ;
36     sh:maxCount 1 ;
37     sh:node aims:PropertyShape ;
38   ] ;
39   owl:imports aims:PropertyShape .
40
```

profile info

Sensor should be linked to metadata describing its capabilities

Sensor should be linked to metadata for the observed property

Validation of already acquired datasets

e.g.
any **results**
that are legit
quantities

```
measurement.shacl.ttl
12 soil:MeasurementShape
13   a sh:NodeShape ;
14   sh:name "measurement"@en ;
15   sh:property [
16     sh:path qdt:hasQuantityKind ;
17     sh:name "quantity"@en;
18     sh:minCount 1 ;
19     sh:maxCount 1 ;
20     sh:class qdt:QuantityKind ;
21   ] ;
22   sh:property [
23     sh:path qdt:applicableUnit ;
24     sh:name "unit"@en;
25     sh:minCount 1 ;
26     sh:maxCount 1 ;
27     sh:class qdt:Unit ;
28   ] ;
```


Temperature sensor

- Quantity: Temperature
- Unit: °Celsius

```
data.ttl
6 ex:TemperatureReading
7   qdt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Temperature ;
8   qdt:applicableUnit unit:DEG_C ;
9   schema:value "20.54513"^^xsd:float .
```


Laser tracker

- Quantity: Length
- Unit: Meter

```
data.ttl
1 ex:TargetPosition
2   qdt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Length ;
3   qdt:applicableUnit unit:M ;
4   schema:value ("-0.226959617"^^xsd:float "-0.3074
```


Validation of already acquired datasets

e.g.
only **results**
that are legit
temperatures

```
temperature_measurement.ttl
7  soil:TemperatureMeasurementShape
8    a sh:NodeShape ;
9    rdfs:label "temperature measurement"@en ;
10   sh:description "A measured temperature value";
11   sh:node soil:MeasurementShape ;
12   owl:imports soil:MeasurementShape ;
13   sh:property [
14     sh:path qudt:hasQuantityKind ;
15     sh:hasValue quantitykind:Temperature;
16   ] ;
17
18
```


Temperature sensor

- Quantity: Temperature
- Unit: °Celsius


```
data.ttl
6  ex:TemperatureReading
7    qudt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Temperature ;
8    qudt:applicableUnit unit:DEG_C ;
9    schema:value "20.54513"^^xsd:float .
```


Laser tracker

- Quantity: Length
- Unit: Meter


```
data.ttl
1  ex:TargetPosition
2    qudt:hasQuantityKind quantitykind:Length ;
3    qudt:applicableUnit unit:M ;
4    schema:value ("-0.226959617"^^xsd:float "-0.3074
```

➔ Individualization of metadata profiles

Publishing Sensor Data & Validated Metadata

Publishing

Ressourcen:

Test 131.76 KB / 1 GB

Name	Geändert	Dateigröße	
NEONDTowerTemperatureData.hdf5	19.10.2022	2.86 MB	
pipeline_runner.py	4.10.2022	5.21 KB	
Heatmap.png	4.10.2022	126.55 KB	

Simulation

Contact *

Creator *

Worked

Worked Note

Title *

Type

Keywords

Subject Area

Creation Date *

Publication Date *

Embargo End Date *

Publishing Sensor Data & Validated Metadata

Receive Metadata

- MetadataHub can interact with productive metadata
- Example:

Simulation

Contact *	<input type="text" value="servicedesk@itc.rwth-aachen.de"/>	✓	+
Creator *	<input type="text" value="Benedikt Heinrichs"/>	✓	+
Worked	<input type="text" value="Yes"/>	▾	+
Worked Note	<input type="text"/>		+
Title *	<input type="text" value="Simulationsmessung"/>	✓	+

MetadataHub Demonstrator

Select the targeted provider

Input your User Token

Select the wanted method

Select the wanted type

Input the metadata path

Response

```
{"id": "document",
  "value": {"data":{"metadataStorage":{"https://hdl.handle.net/21.11102/c2b9012d-13bd-4704-845c-f9374c61eeeb@path=%2FSimulation":
  {"http://purl.org/dc/terms/available":{"value":"2022-10-27"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/created":{"value":"2022-10-18"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/creator":{"value":"Benedikt Heinrichs"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/issued":{"value":"2022-10-19"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/publisher":{"value":"servicedesk@itc.rwth-aachen.de"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/title":{"value":"Simulationsmessung"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"},"type":"literal"},"http://purl.org/dc/terms/type":{"value":"http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Dataset"},"type":"uri"},"http://www.ub.uni-stuttgart.de/dipling#mode":{"value":"https://purl.org/coscine/terms/mode#simulation"},"type":"uri"},"http://www.ub.uni-stuttgart.de/dipling#step":{"value":"1"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"},"type":"literal"},"http://www.ub.uni-stuttgart.de/dipling#version":{"value":"1"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string"},"type":"literal"},"http://www.ub.uni-stuttgart.de/dipling#worked":{"value":"true"},"datatype":"http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#boolean"},"type":"literal"},"http://www.w3.org/1999/02/22-rdf-syntax-"
```

Publishing Sensor Data & Validated Metadata

Receive Metadata

- MetadataHub can interact with productive metadata
- Example:

Simulation

Contact * ✓ +

Creator * ✓ +

Worked ▾ +

Worked Note

Title * ✓ +

MetadataHub Demonstrator

Select the targeted provider

Input your User Token

Select the wanted method

Select the wanted type

Input the metadata path

Response

```
{
  "id": "document",
  "value": {
    "data": {
      "metadataStorage": {
        "url": "https://hdl.handle.net/21.11102/c2b9012d-13bd-4704-845c-f9374c61eeeb@path=%2FSimulation",
        "terms/available": {
          "value": "2022-10-27",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/created": {
          "value": "2022-10-18",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/creator": {
          "value": "Benedikt Heinrichs",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/issued": {
          "value": "2022-10-10",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#date",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/publisher": {
          "value": "servicedesk@itc.rwth-aachen.de",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/title": {
          "value": "Simulationsmessung",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "terms/type": {
          "value": "http://purl.org/dc/dcmitype/Dataset",
          "type": "uri"
        },
        "diplng#mode": {
          "value": "https://purl.org/coscine/terms/mode#simulation",
          "type": "uri"
        },
        "diplng#step": {
          "value": "1",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "diplng#version": {
          "value": "1",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#string",
          "type": "literal"
        },
        "diplng#worked": {
          "value": "true",
          "datatype": "http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#boolean",
          "type": "literal"
        }
      }
    }
  }
}
```

Publishing Sensor Data & Validated Metadata

Searching Metadata

Suchseite:

Datei: [NEONDSTowerTemperatureData.hdf5](#)

Sichtbarkeit: Privat **Erstelldatum:** 2022-03-03 **Erstellungsjahr:** 2022 **Erstellungsmonat:** March **Erstellungstag:** 3 **Date Available:** 2022-03-03
Date Available Year: 2022 **Date Available Month:** March **Date Available Day:** 3 **Ersteller:** Benedikt Heinrichs **Version:** 1
Datenerzeugungsmethode: <https://purl.org/coscine/terms/mode#simulation> **Step:** 1 **Titel:** Test Datei **Publisher:** Heinrichs@itc.rwth-aachen.de
Date Issued: 2022-03-03 **Date Issued Year:** 2022 **Date Issued Month:** March **Date Issued Day:** 3 **Gehört zu Projekt:** Demo Projekt 2022-03-03
Graphname: <https://hdl.handle.net/21.11102/c2f5b5e0-60cf-4cca-86ee-066277d7dd6c@path=%2FNEONDSTowerTemperatureData.hdf5>

Datei: [luh_fdm_umfrage_rohdaten_aggregiert \(1\).xlsx](#)

Sichtbarkeit: Privat **Erstelldatum:** 2022-03-03 **Erstellungsjahr:** 2022 **Erstellungsmonat:** March **Erstellungstag:** 3 **Date Available:** 2022-03-03
Date Available Year: 2022 **Date Available Month:** March **Date Available Day:** 3 **Ersteller:** test **Version:** 1
Datenerzeugungsmethode: <https://purl.org/coscine/terms/mode#simulation> **Step:** 1 **Titel:** Test **Publisher:** Heinrichs@itc.rwth-aachen.de
Date Issued: 2022-03-03 **Date Issued Year:** 2022 **Date Issued Month:** March **Date Issued Day:** 3 **Gehört zu Projekt:** Demo Projekt 2022-03-03
Graphname: [https://hdl.handle.net/21.11102/c2f5b5e0-60cf-4cca-86ee-066277d7dd6c@path=%2FFluh_fdm_umfrage_rohdaten_aggregiert %281%29.xlsx](https://hdl.handle.net/21.11102/c2f5b5e0-60cf-4cca-86ee-066277d7dd6c@path=%2FFluh_fdm_umfrage_rohdaten_aggregiert%281%29.xlsx)

Thanks for your attention!